

FABRICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF TiNi/Al SMART COMPOSITES

G.C. Lee¹, M.G. Kim¹, J.P. Park¹, S.W. Kim¹ and Y.C. Park²

¹ *Research Institute of Industrial Science and Technology, 32 Hyoja-dong, Nam-gu, Pohang, 790-330 Korea*

² *Department of Mechanical Engineering, Dong-A University, 840 Hadan 2-dong, Saha-gu, Busan, 604-714 Korea*

SUMMARY: An attempt was made to fabricate composite material of an aluminum alloy matrix reinforced by TiNi shape memory fiber using a hot-press method and to investigate its microstructures and mechanical properties. The analysis of SEM and EDS showed that the composite material had good interface bonding. The stress-strain behavior of the composite material was evaluated at room temperature and 363 K as a function of pre-strain, and it showed that the yield stress at 363 K is higher than that at room temperature. It is also found that the yield stress of the composite material increased with increasing the amount of pre-strain and depended on the volume fraction of the fiber and heat treatment. The smartness of the composite could be given due to the shape memory effect of the TiNi fiber, which generated compressive residual stress in the matrix material when heated after being pre-strained. Microstructural observation revealed that interfacial reactions occurred between the matrix and fiber, creating two intermetallic layers.

KEYWORDS: Smart composites, Hot-press method, TiNi shape memory fiber, Pre-strain

INTRODUCTION

Many studies have been performed on smart composite material reinforced by TiNi shape memory alloy (SMA) [1-3]. The design concept of this smart composite material is that as temperature increases, austenite transformation occurs from martensite phase in TiNi fiber and the fiber contracts up to the amount of tensile pre-strain applied at room temperature. This property is caused by the shape memory effect (SME) of TiNi fiber and compressive residual stress that occurs in the matrix due to this shape memory effect. As a result, this determines the strength of whole composite material [2,5,6]. Armstrong reported the thermal behavior of Al6061 matrix composite reinforced by TiNi SMA fiber by using a one-dimensional model [4]. He compared the theoretical and experimental results; however, he did not focus on the fabrication process or strengthening mechanism. In addition, Hamada and co-workers [1] reported the optimal fabrication condition for TiNi/Al 6061 composite material in vacuum using the hot-press method. They also reported the strengthening mechanism of composite material by comparison of theoretical and experimental methods. Due to the fabrication method, the volume fraction of fiber is limited so they restricted the volume fraction of fiber within 5.3% and the pre-strain within 2.9%. Thus, the relationship between volume fraction and pre-strain was not thoroughly examined.

This was a fundamental study to develop a fabrication method of TiNi/Al 6061 composite material into plates. In this study, an attempt was made to fabricate a composite material using hot-press method and to examine the strengthening mechanism. There have been many studies in Korea on the fabrication of smart composite material using squeeze casting and powder metallurgy. [7] However, the strength of the smart composite material made by these methods is not satisfactory and many problems, such as array of fiber reinforcement, have occurred. The hot-press method is useful in simultaneously solving strength and fiber array problems. The advantages of the hot-press method are that it can produce various sizes and fiber volume fractions of composite material. In addition, this method allows the production of composite materials into commercially viable plates.

In this study, TiNi/Al 6061 composite material was produced using the hot-press method. To obtain the optimal fabrication condition for composite material, various temperatures and pressures were attempted. The optimal condition was determined by observing the separation of the interface between the fiber and matrix SEM and the diffusion layer as evaluated by EPMA. Three kinds of specimens with volume fractions of fiber 3.2, 5.2 and 7% were made under the optimal condition and their mechanical properties were examined at room temperature and 363 K. To investigate the strength increase effect resulting from pre-strain, 1, 3 and 5% of pre-strain were applied.

DESIGN CONCEPT OF SHAPE MEMORY COMPOSITES MATERIALS

Figure 1 shows the design concept of shape memory composite material. Step 1 is a process to apply tensile force to pre-strain the material, which remains when the tensile force is removed (step 2). In step 3, temperature is raised to 363 K (above A_f) and the reverse transformation occurs from the martensite phase to the austenite phase in TiNi fiber. Then, the pre-strain applied in the superelastic region recovers to the original state (state A_f) due to the shape memory effect. Tension occurs in the matrix metal due to the thermal deformation at 363 K, however, in the matrix metal, compressive stress occurs due to constraint of TiNi fibers. At this time, the elastic modulus of TiNi fiber increases physically. Permanent deformation occurs because of the plastic behavior in the martensite phase. However, elastic recovery occurs under the same load condition since the austenite phase is still in the elastic region. In step 4, tension is applied to step 3 and mechanical properties are evaluated.

Fig. 1: Design concept of smart composite with shape memory reinforcement

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

In this study, 1 mm thick Al 6061 plate and TiNi fiber (Ti-50.0 at % Ni; radius 0.5 mm) are used to fabricate TiNi/Al 6061 shape memory composite material. For the purpose, a hydraulic hot press with a 250-ton capacity is made. This press is equipped with a high temperature furnace that allows maintenance of temperatures up to 973 K. The fixture in figure 2 arrays the fiber shape memory alloy straight at a constant spacing to prevent contact. Similar specimens can be repeatedly made and volume fractions of fiber can be arbitrarily changed. TiNi fiber was fixed at a constant spacing between 150 mm × 22 mm × 1 mm aluminum plates. The aluminum plates were pressurized at high temperature on the press as shown in figure 3. Three kinds of composite materials with three different fiber volume fractions (3.2, 5.2 and 7%) were fabricated for the experiment. To determine the optimal fabrication condition of TiNi/Al 6061 shape memory composite material, two pressures (40 and 60 MPa) were applied for 30 minutes under two temperature conditions (803 and 833 K). Temperature was measured between two aluminum plates and pressure was calculated from the aluminum's dimensions before pressure was applied.

Fig. 2: Fixture for keeping TiNi shape memory alloy fiber

Fig. 3: Schematic diagram of hot pressing method

Since the surface of the aluminum matrix is easily oxidized, the specimens were fabricated in argon. Freeform composite material was made by the hot-press method as shown in figure 4(a). After machining this material, a plate tensile specimen was made. Its shape and dimensions are shown in figure 4(b). To increase the strength of aluminum matrix, T6 heat

treatment was performed. In air, a solution treatment was performed for an hour at 793 K or 813 K, and the specimens were cooled in water. An aging treatment was performed at 448 K.

Fig. 4: The shape of composite freeform and specimen

Figure 5 show the relationship between aging time and hardness. It was observed that the hardness of the composite material solution treated at 813 K was higher than that of 793 K. Previous studies have shown that the hardness does not change significantly after aging treatments of more than 5 hours. In this study; therefore, instead of evaluating the strength of the composite material according to the heat treatment condition, an attempt was made to determine the ideal heat treatment condition to produce the greatest strength of Al 6061 and composite material fabricated under these conditions. Using the results shown figure 5, a solution treatment was performed for the specimen at 813 K for an hour and then an aging treatment was performed at 448 K for 5 hours. Pre-strains of 1, 3 and 5% were applied to the specimen by tensile velocity of 1×10^{-4} mm/s at room temperature. A tensile test was attempted on the pre-strained specimen at 363 K. The experiment temperature was measured at the surface of the specimen by thermocouple.

Fig. 5: The Vickers hardness as a function of aging time

To determine the optimal fabrication condition of TiNi/Al 6061 shape memory composite material using the hot-press method, an evaluation was performed of the adhesion state by SEM and an investigation of the change of chemical composition at the interface of TiNi fiber and Al 6061 matrix was undertaken. The specimen's optimum fabrication volume fraction of fiber was 3.2%. With a volume fraction of 7%, the spacing between two fibers was 0.7 mm, which was wider than the 0.5 mm fiber diameter. Pressure was applied at 833 K. The fiber spacing was found to have no effect on the adhesion state.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To determine the optimal fabrication condition of composite material, three factors (temperature, pressure, and time) were considered. First of all, temperatures affecting diffusion layer are changed to 803 and 833 K respectively, while pressures to 40 MPa and 60 MPa respectively. And then interface connection status varying in accordance with temperature and pressure is observed in the production of composite material by SEM micrograph. Temperature and pressure are kept constant at 1800 seconds. SEM micrographs of the composite materials fabricated by various conditions are shown in figure 6. From the figures, it is observed that the state of adhesion of fiber and matrix differed according to temperature and pressure. At a temperature of 833 K, a pressure of 60 MPa, and a time of 30 minutes in (d), optimal adhesion were attained. In (a), (b) and (c), the adhesion line is observed on the interface of the matrix but perfect adhesion was not formed on the interface between the fiber and matrix.

Fig. 6: SEM micrograph of the TiNi/Al 6061 composite made by various conditions

Fig. 7: EPMA analysis of the interface of fiber and matrix

Figure 7 is a result of EPMA analysis of the portion shown in the rectangular region in figure 6(d). The result demonstrated that the thickness of the diffusion layer is about 400 μm and the component of Ti_xAl_y exists in the diffusion layer. The existence of the diffusion layer is a chemical result between the matrix and fiber and is very important information in the adhesion state of the interface. From the results of SEM and EPMA analysis of interface, 833 K, 60 MPa and 30 minutes were determined to be the optimal condition for the fabrication of TiNi/Al 6061 shape memory composite material.

Fig. 8: Stress-strain curve of TiNi SMA fiber at each temperature (aging time=18000 seconds. pre-strain=0, 1, 3%)

For the evaluation of mechanical properties of TiNi shape memory alloy, the same heat treatment that was applied in the fabrication of the specimen (the temperature of 448 K and maintenance time of 5 hours) was performed. This intended to evaluate the specimen's mechanical properties under the same conditions as matrix Al 6061 that was reinforced by TiNi fiber. The starting temperature of martensite transformation M_s and the finishing temperature of austenite transformation A_f show a gradual increase as the applied stress increases due to the increase martensite transformation. In addition, it has been reported that M_s and A_f at 94 MPa are 296 and 342 K, respectively [8]. Accordingly, in this experiment, at a temperature of 363 K, an evaluation of the mechanical properties was performed. Figure 8 shows the tensile test results of TiNi fiber at room temperature and 363 K. The TiNi fibers for the experiment were pre-strained 0, 1 and 3% at room temperature. Figure 8(a) shows that the stress-strain curves can be divided into an elastic region, super-elastic region, and hardening region of martensite [9, 10]. The super-elastic region is in the 1.5 to 8% range. For TiNi fiber, the effect of pre-strain cannot be observed at room temperature and the strength in the super-elastic region was 284 MPa. On the other hand, at a temperature of 353 K, the elastic and super elastic regions were both present. The strength at the super-elastic region was found to be 715 MPa, which was very high compared with the results obtained at room temperature. In addition, at high temperatures, a slight strength increase due to pre-strain was observed. We concluded from the stress-strain curve of TiNi shape memory alloy that at a high temperature, the increase of volume fraction of fiber was more effective on the strength of TiNi/Al 6061 shape memory composite material than the pre-strain.

A tension test was performed on the specimens with differing volume fractions of fiber (0, 3.2, 5.2 and 7%) to investigate the effect of volume fraction of fiber on the mechanical properties of TiNi/Al 6061 shape memory composite material. The test was performed at room temperature (between M_s and A_f of TiNi fiber) and high temperature (above A_f). In figure 9, stress-strain curves of TiNi/Al 6061 shape memory composite material at room temperature and 363 K are shown and in figure 10, changes of tensile strength due to volume

fraction at room temperature and 363 K are shown. As shown in figure 10, the tensile strength of composite material at room temperature slightly decreased as the volume fraction increased. This infers that the fracture of composite material occurs in the super-elastic region of TiNi shape memory alloy. In figure 8 (a), superelastic region of TiNi fiber indicates the range of strain 1-8%. For yield strength of composite material, the strength of fiber increases in hardened part of martensite, which is out of the range. Figure 9 (a) shows that TiNi/Al 6061 composite material forms general stress-strain curve at normal temperature. This infers that composite material, including separation of interface, is destructed while TiNi fiber exists in superelastic region. In other words, separation of interface occurred due to the difference of strength of fiber and matrix at room temperature. At 363 K; however, tensile strength increased as volume fraction of fiber increased.

Fig. 9: Stress-strain curve of TiNi/Al6061 composite at room temperature and 363K

Contrary to normal temperature, the strength increases at a high temperature of 363 K according to volume content. This could be because the strength of TiNi fiber, reinforcing material, is considerably high at a higher temperature and continuous shape memory remains effective as the fiber stays at superelastic region under tensile strength. However, interface separation of base and basic material is observed on the fractured surface as shown in figure 11. This seems to result from the coefficient difference of heat expansion between the base and the fiber. In order to minimize separation of interface, the diameter of TiNi SMA fiber should be considered in production of composite material because a smaller diameter of TiNi SMA fiber reduces the area of contact between one fiber and matrix, resulting in improvement of joining with matrix compared to a bigger diameter.

Fig. 10: The relationship between volume fraction and tensile strength

Fig. 11: SEM micrographs fracture surface of TiNi/Al 6061 composites

In figure 12, stress-strain curves of different pre-strains are shown. Figure 12 shows that the tensile strength of composite material increases as the amount of pre-strain increases. This is because compressive residual stress occurs at the Al 6061 matrix due to the shape memory effect of TiNi fiber. Above A_s TiNi fiber tends to return to the original state due to shape memory effect. This makes compressive residual stress occur in Al matrix and above A_s the strength of fiber itself also increases. Accordingly, the strength of composite material increases. Figure 12 also reveals that as the volume fraction of fiber increases, large strain occurs in composite material; however, as pre-strain increases, strain in composite material decreases. This is because significant plastic deformation occurs in aluminum as pre-strain increases. Accordingly, it is known that the total elongation of composite material depends on Al 6061, which has a large volume fraction.

(a) $V_f = 3.2\%$

(b) $V_f = 5.2\%$

(c) $V_f = 7\%$

Fig. 12: Stress-strain curves of TiNi/Al 6061 composite

The relationship between tensile strength depending on pre-strain and volume fraction at 363 K is shown in figure 13. It is observed that as the volume fraction of TiNi fiber increases, the tensile strength of composite materials increases almost linearly; and as the volume fraction of fiber increases, tensile strength also increases. On the other hand, as pre-strain increases, the amount of increase of tensile strength tends to be insignificant for composite material of all volume fractions. This is because the increasing effect of strength due to pre-strain of TiNi fiber is slight. Accordingly, it is known that to increase the strength of TiNi/Al 6061 shape memory composite materials it is much more effective to increase the volume fraction of fiber than to increase the pre-strain.

Fig. 13: The relationship between volume fraction and tensile strength as a function of pre-strain at 363K

CONCLUSIONS

This study attempted to determine the fabrication condition of TiNi/Al 6061 shape memory composite material using hot-press method and its mechanical properties. The results are as follows:

- (1) The optimal fabrication condition of TiNi/Al 6061 shape memory composite materials is 833 K, 60 MPa and 30 minutes of maintenance time in hot pressing. In addition, it is verified that diffusion layer exists in the adhesion interface of fiber and matrix according to EPMA analysis.
- (2) The hardness of composite materials solution treated at 813 K is superior to that at 793 K. And after 5-hour aging treatment at 443 K, almost no hardness change occurs in Al 6061 matrix.
- (3) At 363 K, the tensile strength of composite materials with pre-strain increases as the amount of pre-strain increases; however, the amount of increase of strength does not increase noticeably as the amount of pre-strain increases.
- (4) Testing demonstrated that it is more effective to increase the volume fraction of reinforcement fiber to increase the strength of composite materials.
- (5) Slight strength increase due to pure shape memory effect is verified to exist at high temperature

REFERENCES

1. Hamada, K., Lee, J.H., Mizuuchi, K., Taya, M. and Inoue, K., *Metallurgical and Materials Transaction*, Vol. 29A, 1988, pp. 1127-1135.
2. Park, Y.C. and Furuya, Y., *Nondestruction Test Evaluation*, Vol. 4, 1992, pp. 541~554.
3. Furuya, Y., *Proceeding of the International Symposium on the Microsystems, Intelligent Materials and Pobots*, Sendai, Japan, 1995, pp.313~318.
4. Armstrong, W.D., *Jouranal of Intelligent Materials System Structure*, Vol. 7, 1996, pp. 448~453.
5. Ehren Stein, H., *Proceeding of the International Conference on Material Transformation*, 1986, pp.1083~1086.
6. Hunag, Y., Yang, G., and He, P., *Scripta Metallurgica*, Vol. 19, 1985, pp. 1033~1038
7. Park, Y.C., Yun, D.P., Lee, G.C. and Furuya, Y., *Transactions of the KSME*, Vol. A 21, 1997, pp. 405~413.
8. Fujii, T. T., and Zako, M., *Real Number Edition*, Inc., Tokyo, Japan, 1996, pp.13-16.
9. Wayman, C.M., *Journal of the Japan Institute Metals*, Vol. 19, 1980, pp. 26~32.
10. Park, Y.C., Oh, S.W., Cho, Y.B., Hue, D.W. and Lee, M.Y., *Korea Society of Coastal and Ocean Engineers*, Vol. 6, 1992, pp.87~95.